

SELF-EFFICACY AND BULLYING PREVALENCE AMONG CRIMINOLOGY STUDENTS IN GENERAL SANTOS CITY

¹JOBELLE I. LORENZO, (PhD. Crim), ²MARNIE J. BESAS, (PhD. Crim)

College Of Criminal Justice

Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Colleges

General Santos City, Philippines

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Abstract: This investigation was conducted to figure out which domain of self-efficacy best impacts bullying prevalence as this can bring issues to light to the planned recipients and potentially create activity that intends to enhance the school organization. The study used non-experimental design and correlational technique. The findings of this were specific to the Criminology students in General Santos City. There were 305 Criminology students as samples determined through Slovin's formula and stratified random sampling procedure. Results demonstrated that the level of self-efficacy among Criminology Students is high; there is a noteworthy connection between bullying prevalence and self-efficacy and there is a positive critical connection between bullying predominance and self-efficacy as uncovered in the trial of relationship. The domain that best influences bullying prevalence is pro-social.

Keywords: Criminal justice, bullying prevalence, self-efficacy, criminology, students, Philippines.

1. INTRODUCTION

Rationale

Bullying and companion exploitation in schools have turned out to be serious worries for understudies, guardians, instructors, and the school authorities in the United States of America and around the globe (Hong & Espelage, 2012). It has turned into a kind of savagery that debilitates a youngster's prosperity and all the more particularly in school. School bullying and peer exploitation are real social issues influencing kids and youths in all parts of the world (Hong & Espelage, 2012). Youngsters who bully may likewise encounter negative emotional well-being impacts, for example, dejection, self-destructive ideation, and mental pain (Bauman, Toomey & Walker 2012; Vanderbilt & Augustyn, 2010). Kokkinos and Kipritsi, (2012) recommended that these individuals would get the part of the protector in bullying circumstances. Individuals with low self-efficacy in these spaces will probably create maladaptive conduct and may probably take up the part of the domineering jerk, collaborator to the bully or victim.

Self-efficacy can be believed to assume a basic part in whether understudies get associated with by standing practices or stay uninvolved. (Tsung, Hui & Law 2011; Thornberg & Jungert, 2013; Poyhonen, Juvonen & Salmivalli, 2010). Helping a companion who is getting defrauded in a bullying circumstance can be to a great degree an unsafe undertaking, as the individual who winds up included in the interest of the victim is confronting a threatening harasser and is in danger of turning into a victim themselves. Along these lines the individuals should be sure about their capacity to mediate successfully, in the event that they do not trust that they have the capacity to intercede in the bullying circumstance adequately, they are far less inclined to do as such regardless of whether they are in contradiction of the bullying conduct

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(Tsung et al, 2011; Thornberg&Jungert, 2013; Poyhonen et al, 2012). A man's self- efficacy in specific areas throughout his life can influence how he carries on in bullying circumstances. Individuals with high self- efficacy in scholastic exhibitions and social collaboration will probably manage issues in a protecting and tension free house (Kokkinos &Kipritsi, 2012).

The study of Seixas, Coelho and Gustave(2013) show that understanding confidence as another well' being and prosperity mental marker, a few investigations have exhibited that bullies, victims, and the understudies not engaged with bullying practices vary in their levels of confidence. Awesome comparison has been seen in the outcomes acquired by various examinations, in various nations, with understudies from 7 to 16 years of age. By and large, victims display measurably bring down levels of confidence than the rest of the understudies.

In General Santos City, A 20-year-old student residing at Brgy. Calumpang was arrested because of publishing bad statements on her social media account. Through social media she bullied a 16 yrs. old teenage girl student in which she posted the name of the student on her social media account. According to region 12 anti-cybercrime, Ellen Jane Amado was arrested because of libel case (Canlas, 2017).

The analyst has never come across of an examination on bullying commonness and self- efficacy among criminology understudies. It is in this setting the specialist is intrigued to decide if the self- efficacy impacts the bullying predominance as this can bring issues to light to the proposed recipients of this examination and potentially create activity that intends to enhance school organization, subsequently, the need to lead this investigation.

Research Objective

The main thrust of the study is to find out which domain of self-efficacy best influences bullying prevalence among criminology students in General Santos City, it sought to answer the following objectives:

1. To describe the self-efficacy among criminology students in terms of :
 - 1.1 enlisting social resources;
 - 1.2 academic achievement; and
 - 1.3 self-regulated Learning.
2. To assess the bullying prevalence of criminology students in terms of:
 - 2.1 bully;
 - 2.2 victim; and
 - 2.3 pro social.
3. To determine the significant relationship between self-efficacy and bullying prevalence among criminology students in General Santos City.
4. To determine which domain of self-efficacy best influences bullying prevalence among criminology students in General Santos City.

Hypothesis

The accompanying speculations will be tried at 0.05 level of importance:

1. There is no noteworthy connection between self- efficacy and bullying predominance of criminology understudies.
2. There is no domain in the self-efficacy that best influences bullying prevalence of criminology students.

Review of Related Literature

Presented in this section are readings from the related literature, different books, journals, articles, and internet written by different authors relevant to the present research. The researcher focused on bullying prevalence and self-efficacy among criminology students in General Santos City.

The independent variable of the study is the self-efficacy whose indicators *Enlisting Social Resources, Academic Achievement and Self-regulated learning* by (Bandura, 2006). On the other hand, the dependent variable is the bullying prevalence as cited by Ken Rigby and Philip Slee (1993) whose indicators are *Bully, Victim and Pro-social*.

In a desire to hand over adequate literatures regarding the bullying prevalence and self-efficacy among criminology students, the researcher spent plenty of time in reading varied books, theses, and internet resources which have bearing to the present study and are presented in this section.

Self-Efficacy

Self-efficacy is a man's conviction on how able he is on a specific issue, to be specific extremely well, not exceptionally well or feeble. Understudies who see their exhibitions to be more satisfactory than it really is have a tendency to be more fruitful in their exhibitions. Therefore, if people apparent self-efficacy is high, his execution really achieves more elevated amounts however in the event that his self-efficacy is low, he performs under his level of limit (Gun & Yildiz, 2014). Ozmentes (2014) announced another factor that influences learning is the "self-efficacy belief" which can be characterized as the individual conviction of an understudy to accomplish a particular errand. Bandura (2006) understood that a people's contemplation of adequacy and self-completion in a vocation underlies that people desire towards the after effect of that activity and he characterizes self-efficacy as self-capability that a man has so as to organize and realize required employments for achieving the objective.

In the investigation of Clark (2013) Clark and Zimmerman (2014) self-control has uncovered that for all intents and purposes all levels of learning undertakings, when students take part in self-administrative procedures, for example, objective setting, self-checking, self-assessment, and self-reflection, understudies accomplish abnormal amounts of individual, scholastic, and expert results in differing settings and social spaces.

Bullying Prevalence

Bullying is an exceptionally complex marvel and may happen in a wide range of structures and among various gatherings of understudies (e.g., ethnic social or sexual minorities and dominant parts) Llorent, Ortega and Zych (2016) integrated investigations on the commonness of bullying in various settings.

An aggregate of 80 thinks about from various geographic zones were incorporated, and it was discovered that the mean commonness rates of contribution in bullying, over these reports, were 35% for execution and 36% for exploitation. It merits specifying that the criteria used to compute the pervasiveness rates contrasted extraordinarily among the included examinations, with some of them characterizing youngsters as included who announced even extremely mellow types of bullying and others, then again, requiring more serious structures. Subsequently, the after effects of the meta-examination demonstrate that 35% of understudies are associated with some type of bullying, including its gentle or extreme cases.

In Asia, a survey of concentrates in China demonstrates exploitation rates going from 2 to 66% and execution rates going from 2 to 34% (Chan & Wong, 2015). Another audit demonstrates that bullying exists likewise in Southeast Asian Countries with pervasiveness rates of having been bullied on over 10 days amid the previous 30 days somewhere in the range of 1 and 7.7% (Sittichai & Smith, 2015). In the UK, an ongoing report discharged by the Anti-Bullying Alliance (2015) looked into inquire about on bullying directed in the nation since 2010. Among the 102 School Bullying in Different Countries: Prevalence, Risk examine on the predominance rates of bullying, an investigation led with 11,000 optional instruction understudies in England and ridges demonstrated that 33% of the members announced having been bullied some of the time and 11% a great deal (BIG 2015). Comparative examinations were directed in Scotland and Northern Ireland and more points of interest can be found in the Anti-Bullying Alliance report (2015).

Understudies who take part in bullying conduct are at expanded hazard for scholastic issues, substance utilization, and fierce conduct later in pre-adulthood and adulthood. Understudies who are the focus of bullying and participate in bullying conduct are at more serious hazard for both emotional well-being and conduct issues than understudies who just bully or are just bullied (Center for Disease Control, 2015). The view of Canty, Stubbe, Steers & Collings, S. (2014) call attention to that such 'preparing' may darken youngsters' genuine experience. It likewise ignores the way that every youngster is in a functioning procedure of 'understanding and generation of the way of life around them'. It is conceivable that youngsters may react to 'tormenting' as a stacked term related with grown-up produced ideas.

Then again, Salmivalli (2014) state that a few observers engaged with bullying play an alternate part and endeavour to help the victim. Research shows that a noteworthy positive distinction can result for a victim when they are upheld by onlookers or shielded against their domineering jerk by an observer instead of just watched.

Moreover, Popp, Peguero, Day and Kahle (2014) announced that exploitation may make individuals dread for their wellbeing instead of their instructive results. Likewise, because of bullying, a victim may have bring down levels of mental prosperity which thus can diminish their general instructive accomplishment.

Additionally, the Center for Disease Control (2015) surmise that the victim and the domineering jerk are in danger for negative impacts of bullying. In any case, it clarifies that even the onlookers of bullying may encounter some negative outcomes from simply seeing bullying. Understudies who encounter bullying are at expanded hazard for poor school change, rest troubles, nervousness, and wretchedness. Among secondary school understudies, 15.5% are cyberbullied and 20.2% are bullied on school property. Among center school understudies, 24% are cyber-bullied and 45% are bullied on school property (Center for Disease Control, 2015). The rates of people who have encountered cyberbullying sooner or later in their lifetimes have about multiplied (18% to 34%) from 2007-2016 (Patchin&Hinduja, 2016). 90% of youngsters report's identity cyber-bullied have additionally been bullied disconnected ("Seven Fears and the Science of How Mobile Technologies May Be Influencing Adolescents in the Digital Age," George, Russell &Odgers, 2015).

The last domain is *pro-social*. The terms "prosocial youngsters" or "prosocial conduct" will be utilized to allude to protector like conduct among preschool kids. Cases of prosocial conduct in more established understudies incorporate endeavouring to shield the victim from the forceful conduct by putting a stop to it, revealing it to a grown-up, or getting to be companions with the victim since prosocial conduct have not been inspected among preschool youngsters widely, we must draw data about protectors from the exploration on more seasoned kids and adolescents. Children who guard others likely have high compassion, are all around preferred by their associates, and have a solid encouraging group of people (Camodeca, Caravita& Coppola, 2014; Monks, Ortega Ruiz &TorradoVai, 2002).

Youngsters with prosocial propensities have a tendency to have enough created dialect and social abilities. Youngsters who have developed social abilities will probably have the capacity to manage themselves. Self-regulation could help ease issue conduct that happen after some time, for example, hostility. Youngsters with great self direction can pick up kinships and furthermore diminish the probability of being bullied (Flook, Goldberg, Pinger& Davidson, 2015) People with this specific arrangement of abilities are likewise ready to make companionships all the more effortlessly. Youngsters can increase social competency through social encounters. He likewise gave preschool kids the chance to cooperate with peers amid a sharing examination. The outcomes demonstrate that kids inside the preschool age range can take part in prosocial conduct (ie., sharing), anyway they should have introduction. Social competency can assume a vast part in anticipating bullying or non-bullying conduct with youthful youngsters.

Social fitness is a basic defensive factor for a youngster and their change in accordance with specific circumstances, which will enable them to connect with and interface fittingly (Camodeca, Caravita& Coppola, 2015). Compassion and declaration appear to be critical social abilities in connection to bullying part conduct, in any event among rudimentary and center school kids (Jenkins, Demaray, Secord, & Summers, 2014; Jenkins & Nickerson, 2016).

The study conducted by Kassem (2015) on bullying behaviour and general self-efficacy among the studied nursing students; the result revealed that there was a significant relationship between bullying behaviour and general self-efficacy among the studied nursing students.

The foregoing presentation and discussion of various literatures had helped bring into the focus the importance on the influence of bullying prevalence and self-efficacy among criminology students. The literature presented had also helped the researcher realize that self-efficacy has a great influence on bullying prevalence among criminology students.

Theoretical Framework

The study was anchored on the proposition of Tsung et al. (2011) that high levels of self-efficacy are associated with the defender role and low levels of self-efficacy are associated with the role of the bully and the victim. This proposition is taken as the framework of the study since it covers the interaction of the two variables in this research. The proposition shows the important role of self-efficacy in bullying prevalence. This proposition was considered since it presents the notion how self-efficacy may affect the bullying prevalence.

In support of this proposition, Kokkinos and Kipritsi (2012) stated that individuals with abnormal amounts of self-efficacy are more ready to manage issues in a protecting and nervousness free house. While individuals with low self-efficacy will probably create maladaptive practices which drives them to take up the part of the domineering jerk or the victim. A man's self-efficacy in specific spaces throughout their life can influence how they act in bullying circumstances. It may be recommended that these individuals would get the part of the safeguard in bullying circumstances. Individuals with low self-efficacy in these areas will probably create maladaptive conduct and may probably take up the part of the domineering jerk, right hand to the bully or the victim.

In parallel, Tsunget al. (2011) states that their Research on self-efficacy and the bullying propose that self-viability decidedly influences expert social conduct with understudies high in self-proficiency convictions more inclined to help out the victim while those with low levels of self-efficacy convictions are unquestionably liable to not mediate by any means. Thornberg and Jungert (2013) expressed that in their investigation abnormal amounts of self-efficacy propelled and drew in young people to encourage the victim, while low levels of self-efficacy repressed them from interceding.

Conceptual Framework

Shown in Figure 1 is the conceptual paradigm of the study showing the relationship between the variables of the study. The independent variable is self-efficacy of criminology students with the three indicators modified and adopted from Bandura (2006).

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework Showing the Variables of the Study

The first indicator is *Enlisting social resources* in self-efficacy which refers to the help rendered by a peers and teachers to a student when a social problem occurs. The second indicator is *Academic achievement* which is the outcome of education — the extent to which a student, teacher or institution has achieved their educational goals. The last indicator is *Self-regulated learning* which refers to learning that is guided by metacognition (planning, monitoring, and evaluating personal progress against a standard), and motivation to learn.

On the other hand the dependent variable is the bullying prevalence with three indicators adopted and modified from Ken Kigby and Philip Slee (1993). The first indicator is *Bully* the use of force, threat, or coercion to abuse, intimidate, or aggressively dominate others. The second indicator is *Victim* it refers to a person who experienced bullying. The last indicator *Pro social* it refers to a social behaviour that benefits other people or society as a whole such as helping, sharing, donating and volunteering.

Significance of the Study

Bullying is unpredictable. It opposes oversimplified thoughts and arrangements. Knowing precisely what bullying is and understanding why it happens are basic to discovering positive and enduring answers for everybody included. Understudies can assume different parts inside the bullying dynamic. Bullying of any frame or for any reason can have long haul negative effects on everybody included including onlookers. Students who are bullied are more likely to feel disconnected from school and not like school, have lower academic outcomes, including lower attendance and completion rates, lack quality friendships at school, display high levels of emotion that indicate vulnerability and low levels of resilience be less well accepted by peers, avoid conflict and be socially withdrawn, have low self-esteem have depression, anxiety, feelings of

loneliness and isolation, have nightmares, feel wary or suspicious of others have an increased risk of depression and substance abuse in extreme cases, have a higher risk of suicide, however, the reasons why a person may be at risk of suicide are extremely complicated.

The topic of bullying is not a new development in the school environment; bullying in various forms has been a significant problem affecting students of all ages for decades. According to an article in the School Psychology Review, 70.6% of young people say they have seen bullying in their schools. Similarly, a large-scale study found that about 49% of children in grades 4-12 reported being bullied by other students at school at least once during the past month.

The clear prevalence of bullying as a pervasive issue in schools across the country necessitates that educators take action to stop and prevent bullying within their educational spheres. It is important because bullying in all forms can have a seriously detrimental, long-term impact on not only the victim, but also on other students exposed to the activities.

Self-efficacy can enormously affect how criminology understudies feel, think, carry on, and inspire themselves. Individuals who have an uplifted feeling of self-efficacy: See testing issues as assignments to be averted, as opposed to dangers to be kept away from. Create more prominent inherent intrigue and center in their exercises. Set testing objectives and exhibit a more grounded feeling of promise to them. Rapidly recuperate their self-efficacy following misfortunes and dissatisfactions (Bandura, 1994).

Individuals who have a low feeling of self-efficacy: stay away from troublesome undertakings and view them as individual dangers. Have a frail responsibility to their objectives and trust that troublesome assignments and circumstances are past their capacities. Harp on individual failings and negative results, rather how to succeed. They rapidly lose confidence in their own capacities and effortlessly create melancholy and stress (Bandura, 1994). Moreover individuals who have high self-efficacy tend to learn and accomplish more than those with low self-efficacy, notwithstanding when real capacity levels are the same (Ormrod, 2008).

Definition of Terms

To make this study clear and comprehensive to understand for the readers, the following terms are operationally defined:

Bullying Prevalence. As used in this study, it refers to the pervasive unwelcome verbal, written, physical or emotional conduct directed at or about a student by another student which includes bully, victim and pro-social.

Self-efficacy. As used in this study, it refers to the extent or strength of one's belief in one's own ability to complete tasks and reach goals which includes enlisting social resources, academic achievement and self-regulated learning.

2. METHOD

Presented in this chapter are the discussions on the research design, the research locale, the population and sample, the research instrument, the data collection, statistical tools, and ethical considerations.

Research Design

The examination utilized non-test configuration utilizing correlational procedure. In this plan, the current condition is engaged. As illustrated by Kowalczyk (2015), it is how much an occasion, factor, wonder, or variable is related with, identified with, or can be anticipated from another; how much the straight relationship exists between factors, estimated by a correlational coefficient. Factual systems used to decide how much (at least two) factors fluctuate together. Correlational study does not propose a reason impact relationship but rather just the level of parallelism or concomitance between the factors, the reason for which might be known. This outline was fitting in deciding the harassing predominance and self-efficacy among criminology students understudy in General Santos City (Gensan).

Research Locale

This study was conducted at General Santos City. It was conducted in the month of June 19 to 20 school year 2017 among four criminology schools in Gensan where the study was conducted. Appeared in Figure 2 is the guide of the Philippines featuring the region of South Cotabato and the area of the General Santos City. The City of General Santos (Cebuano: Dakbayansa Heneral Santos; Hiligaynon: Dakbanwa/Syudad sang Heneral Santos; Filipino: Lungsod ng Heneral Santos; formerly known as Dadiangás, and contracted G.S.C. or on the other hand GenSan), is the southernmost city in the

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Philippines. Considered as a profoundly urbanized five star city, General Santos is the fifteenth most crowded city in the nation with 594,446 residents according to 2015 evaluation. General Santos City is the provincial community for business and industry of the Soccsksargen area, and geologically situated inside the region of South Cotabato.

Population and Sample

The respondents of the study were specific to the criminology students of General Santos City for the month of June 19 to October 20 2017-2018. The teaching and non-teaching personnel were not included in the selection of the respondents to consistently align the study of the bullying prevalence and self-efficacy among Criminology Students which is the specialization of the researchers. The participation of respondents was voluntary. The refusal of the respondents to participate involved no penalty or loss of benefits to which the respondents are otherwise entitled. The respondents may withdraw their consent at any time and discontinue participation without penalty.

Shown in the distribution of respondents, the actual number of respondents in Cronasia College is 341, Filipino Canadian Community College Inc is 68, Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Colleges is 1,386, Villamor College is 38 students. The total number of criminology students involved in the study is 1,833.

Distribution of Respondents

School	Criminology Students	Samples	Percentage
Cronasia College Inc.	341	57	19
Filipino Canadian Community College Inc	68	12	4
Ramon Magsaysay Memorial College	1386	230	75
Villamor College	38	6	2
Total	1833	305	100

The samples were selected at random and 305 students were the respondents in the study from the different Criminology schools in General Santos City. The samples were determined through Slovin’s formula and stratified sampling.

As per Ary, Jacobs and Razavieh, (2002) favourable position of stratified examining is that it enables the specialist to consider contrasts among different subgroups of a populace and ensures portrayal of characterized bunches in the populace. Likewise, Fraenkel and Wallen (2006) emphasize that stratified arbitrary examining improves the probability of representativeness, particularly if the example in not substantial. They proposed that the disservice requires more exertion with respect to the analyst. The Slovin Formula was used to identify the total samples of criminology students. According to Ariola (2006) Slovin’s equation enables a specialist to test the populace with a coveted level of exactness. It gives the scientist a thought of how expansive his example estimate should be to guarantee a sensible precision of results.

Research Instrument

The instrument used in the study has two parts, the first part was on the self-efficacy adopted and modified from Bandura (2006) and the second part is the survey questionnaire for bullying prevalence which was adopted from Ken Rigby and Philip Slee (1993). The original questionnaire was modified to contextualize the school setting and the question items were simplified for the understanding of the respondents. The instrument was subjected for dry run in order to determine the Cronbach Alpha values before content validation by experts with an external validator. The expert summary rating and comments garnered an overall rating of three with a descriptive rating of good. The questionnaires were administered to the identified respondents of the study.

Data Collection

After the approval of the panel members, the researchers underwent the following steps and procedures in gathering the data for the study.

A permission letter was sent to the different criminology schools in General Santos City to conduct a study on Bullying Prevalence and Self-efficacy of Criminology students. Upon the approval, the researcher informed and asked permission from every school head to conduct study in their schools with the coordination of the guidance counselor. The researcher personally administered the survey questionnaire, the first school that she administered the survey was her very own school where she worked at which was Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Colleges. Followed by Cronasia College, Filipino Canadian Community College Inc. and Villamor College that near her working place.

Before the proper administering of the survey test, every item was explained to the respondents in Filipino or in vernacular if needed for a better understanding of every item. The survey was conducted in the whole month of July 2017. Though there were hardships during the process of administering the survey, the researcher was still glad and blessed to experience such challenges that made her become more persistent to continue her thesis. The researcher personally collected the completed questionnaires. The data gathered were tallied based from the sub-problems of this study and treated using the appropriate statistical tools. A simple token of appreciation was given to the respondents as an expression of gratitude for the valuable support, participation and cooperation in answering the survey questions. The data collected was recorded in coordination with the statistician.

Statistical Tools

The information assembled through the survey was counted and treated utilizing the accompanying measurable devices:

Mean. This was computed to describe the bullying prevalence and self-efficacy of criminology students.

Pearson r. This was applied to test the significant relationship between the bullying prevalence and self-efficacy of criminology students.

Regression. This was employed to determine the significant influence of bullying prevalence and self-efficacy among Criminology Students in General Santos City.

Ethical Considerations

All students who participated in the evaluation is free from coercion. Participants are free to withdraw their participation at any time without negatively impacting on their involvement in future services or the current program and relationships with any of the researchers or research bodies involved. It is the right of participants to leave a program of this nature at any time; therefore no pressure should be placed on those who choose not to continue. Explanations are also not required. Respondents were made aware of the questionnaire that any information they provided in this study was kept anonymous and confidential.

The respondents in the evaluation are fully informed about the evaluation being conducted. They are aware of the purpose of this study and how the findings will be used, the respondent is able to make an informed decision as to whether they will participate in the evaluation or not. The research questionnaire is free of technical terms and is easily understandable to the respondents of the study. It provides the population a clear view of benefits the students may generate after the conduct of the study. The research questionnaire will be administered with the consent and support of the authorities of the school administration. Therefore, no research questionnaire will be given to any teaching and non-teaching personnel of the school without the permission from the authorized command channels.

The respondents of this study are all criminology students in General Santos City, regardless of their age, sex, year level and tribe. The distribution of respondents as reflected in table 1 will show how the population is being disseminated. Furthermore, the data collection procedures indicate, as well, how the questionnaires are being administered and the manner the population are going to be involved in the study.

The study excluded the risk situations that the population may experience in the area of physical, psychological, or socio-economic concerns. The useful and relevant information acquired from this study would be of great help to the criminology students. Self-efficacy can greatly impact how criminology students feel, think, behave, and motivate themselves. This group also may use this study as an example to bear in their mind they are luckier than those who are bullied even if life is very difficult because of economic problems, they are still sent in the school to learn by their parents, thus changing them and enabling them to perform well in class, to upgrade their knowledge and intelligence. The respondents did not receive

any incentives for taking part in this research. Copyright infringement is, maybe, the most widely recognized type of research unfortunate behaviour. Specialists must know to refer to all sources and take cautious notes. Utilizing or speaking to crafted by others as your own work constitutes copyright infringement, regardless of whether conferred accidentally. While checking on advantaged data, for example, while auditing stipends to diary article compositions for peer survey, specialists must perceive that what they are perusing cannot be utilized for their own motivations since it cannot be referred to until the point that the work is distributed or openly accessible.

Fabrication is the development and additionally option of information, perceptions, or portrayals that never happened in the get-together of information or running of examinations. Manufacture can happen when "rounding out" whatever remains of examination runs, for instance. Claims about outcomes should be made on entire informational indexes (as is regularly accepted), where claims made in view of inadequate or expected outcomes is a type of creation. A conflict of interest arises when one's judgment is compromised based on connections, favors, or competing interests, and/or when one's position is used to gain favor or extra rewards. Conflicts of interest are not always immediately obvious, nor does a conflict of interest in-and-of-itself constitute wrongdoing.

While the researcher conducted the study at different criminology schools in General Santos City the researcher employed the overt operation. The researcher secured a written permission from different Criminology Schools in General Santos City in which the letters were submitted to the Dean's Office for the approval with the coordination with the guidance counselor to conduct the study in their respective schools. The researchers is the one who made the study possible. The researchers received the credits, responsibility and has the right to publish this study.

3. RESULTS

The data on Bullying Prevalence and Self-efficacy among Criminology Students are presented in this section. The order of the presentation is based on the objectives as follows: To describe the self- efficacy among criminology students in terms of *Enlisting social resources, Academic achievement & Self-regulated Learning*; To assess the bullying prevalence of criminology students in terms of *Bully, Victim, & Pro Social*; To determine the significant relationship between bullying prevalence and self-efficacy among criminology students in General Santos City; and To determine which of the domains best influence the self-efficacy and bullying prevalence among criminology students in General Santos City.

Level of Self-Efficacy among Criminology Students

The first objective of this study was to determine the level of self-efficacy among criminology students. The level of self-efficacy in terms of *Enlisting Social Resources, Academic Achievement, and Self-Regulated Learning*.

Shown in Table 1 is the level of self-efficacy of criminology students. The over-all mean score of the said variable obtained 3.68 which indicates a high level with a standard deviation of 0.75.

From this result, identified *academic achievement* has the highest mean score of 3.98 which signifies *high descriptive level*, *self-regulated learning* with a mean score of 3. 87 which also denotes a *high level descriptive*.

Table 1: Level of Self-efficacy of Criminology Students

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Academic Achievement	0.99	3.98	High
Self-Regulated Learning	0.91	3.87	High
Enlisting Social Resources	0.89	3.19	Moderate
Overall	0.75	3.68	High

Enlisting social resources with a mean score of 3.19 which signify *moderate descriptive level*.

Data from the appended table 1.2, indicator *academic achievement* obtained a mean score of 3.98 which was a result from the individual items in the questionnaire. These items demonstrated areas/subjects like *learning criminalistics, 3.96; criminal law and jurisprudence,3.94; crime detection & investigation,3.99; law enforcement administration,4.09; correctional administration,3.92; and learn sociology of crimes ethics and human relations,3.97*. The result represents that criminology students in General Santos City learned a lot from their academics.

The second highest indicator is the *self-regulated learning*, which obtained a mean score of 3.87 and denotes a *high level*. These items demonstrated statements like, *finishing homework assignment by deadlines,3.81; always concentrating on school subjects during class,3.90; planning schoolwork for the day,3.68; taking good notes during class instruction,3.94; getting oneself to do schoolwork,4.0*.

Lastly, the lowest indicator is *enlisting social resources* demonstrated a *moderate level* with a mean score of 3.19. These items include, *asking teacher for help when stuck on schoolwork,3.07; asking another student for help when stuck on school work,3.26; asking adults for help when having social problems,3.20; asking a friend for help when having special problems,3.29; asking a mentor for help when having social problems,3.13*.

Level of Bullying Prevalence among Criminology Students

The second objective was to determine the level of *BullyingPrevalence* which was measured through a survey questionnaire with the following indicators: *Bully, Victim and Pro-social*.

Presented in Table 2 is the respondents’ response on the level of Bullying Prevalence among Criminology Students with an over-all mean of 2.85 which denotes a moderate level with the standard deviation of 0.71 that most of the respondents regarded the Bullying Prevalence of Criminology Student as moderate. It can be seen that *pro-social* obtained a mean score of 3.72 which shows *High descriptive level*, 2.52 in *victim* and 2.31 in *bully* which show *low descriptive level*.

Table 2: Level of Bullying Prevalence among Criminology Students

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Pro Social	1.06	3.72	High
Victim	0.99	2.52	Low
Bully	1.06	2.31	Low
Overall	0.71	2.85	Moderate

The following are the aspects that contribute to the moderate level of bullying prevalence of criminology students as shown in appended Table 2.3: The highest indicator is *Pro-Social* shows evidently a high level with a mean score of 3.72 which further shows a high level from the respondents. The mean score obtained from the sub-indicators; *liking to make friends, 3.87; liking to help students being harassed,3.54; liking to share things with others,3.58; liking to help friends being harassed,3.61; and enjoying helping others, 3.98*. This shows that the *Pro-Social* among criminology students is rated as high. The second highest indicator *Victim* obtained a mean score of 2.52 which denotes low level. The said indicator comprises; *getting called names by others,2.60; getting picked on by others,2.45; making fun by others,2.84; getting hit and punished around others,2.28; and leaving out things on purpose,2.41*.

Consequently, the lowest indicator is *Bully* demonstrated a low level with a mean score of 2.31 from the test items rated by the respondents. These items include; *giving soft school/ classmates a hard time,2.47; going around teasing others, 2.47; liking to make others scared,2.34; enjoying upsetting wimps, 2.25; and liking to get in fights with someone they can easily beat, 2.05*.

Significance on the Relationship between Self-efficacy on Bullying Prevalence among Criminology Students

The most important purpose of this study was to determine whether or not the self-efficacy of criminology is significantly related with their bullying prevalence. Shown in Table 3 are the correlations between bullying prevalence and self-efficacy among criminology students in General Santos City. Significance is shown from the over-all r-value .274 with p-value .000 lesser than .05 alpha level. There is a positive correlation between the two variables which further imply that the higher the

level of self-efficacy, the lower is the level of the bullying prevalence among the respondents. Hence, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between bullying prevalence and self-efficacy among criminology students in General Santos City was rejected.

Furthermore, the r-values and p-values of some indicators also show significant relationship. When Enlisting social resources is correlated to Pro-social, the results show r-value .294 and p-value less than 0.05 which evidently show a significant relationship between the two. This can be seen also when enlisting social resources correlated with Bully; the results show r-value of .178 and p-value less than 0.05 which indicate significant relationship.

Table 3: Significance on the Relationship between Self-efficacy on Bullying Prevalence

Self-efficacy	Bullying Prevalence			Overall
	Bully	Victim	Pro-social	
Enlisting social resources	.178** (0.001)	.267** (0.000)	.294** (0.000)	.359** .000
Academic achievement	-.063 (0.252)	-.031 (0.571)	.454** (0.116)	0.179* (0.001)
Introjected Regulation	-.105 (0.057)	-.077 (1.62)	0.446** (0.000)	0.425* (0.000)
Overall	0.000 (0.997)	0.060 (0.275)	0.495** (0.000)	0.274** (0.000)

P < .05

The second indicator is *academic achievement* when correlated to *Pro social*, demonstrated the r-value .454 and p-value less than 0.05 which indicate significant relationship. When the indicator *Academic achievement* is correlated with indicators *Victim* and *Bully*, the result produced r-values -.063 and -.031 with p-values of .252 and .571 both more than 0.05 shows no significant relationship between indicators.

Consequently, the third indicator is *self-regulated learning* is correlated to *Pro-social* the r-value .466 and p-value less than 0.05 with significant relationship. When the *Academic achievement* is correlated with indicators *Victim* & *Bully* the result produced r-values -.105 and -.077 with p-values .057 and .162 it shows no significant relationship between the indicators.

The over-all r-value .274 and p-value less than 0.05 significantly show relationship among variables. These further mean that bullying prevalence as a whole with indicators: *Bully*, *Victim* and *Pro Social* are significantly correlated with self-efficacy of respondents across three indicators *Enlisting social resources*, *Academic achievement* and *Self-regulated learning*.

Significance on the Influence of Self-Efficacy on Bullying Prevalence among Criminology Students

Table 4 illustrates the regression analysis on the influence of self-efficacy on bullying prevalence of criminology students. Using the Regression Analysis the data revealed that the overall self-efficacy significantly influence the bullying prevalence among criminology students since the self-efficacy on bullying prevalence has the F value of 35.416 with the overall p-value less than 0.05 which indicate that there is significant influence of self-efficacy on bullying prevalence of criminology students. The R² value of .247 implies that 24.7 percent of the variance of the bullying prevalence can be explained by self-efficacy and the remaining 75.3 percent is attributed by other factors. The coefficient of determination value or the r denotes that .247 of the variation in self-efficacy of criminology students is explained by the variance in prevalence of bullying.

Table 4: Multiple Regression Analysis on the Influence of the Prevalence of Bullying on Self-Efficacy of Criminology Students

Self-Efficacy					
Prevalence of Bullying	B (Standardized Coefficients)	B (Unstandardized Coefficients)	T	Sig.	
Bully	0.031	0.044	0.701	0.484	
Victim	-.008	-.010	-.158	0.874	
Pro Social	0.355	0.500	10.182	0.000	
R	0.497				
R ²	0.247				
F	35.416				
P	0.000				

As shown in the table, *Bully and Victim* obtained p-values of .484 and .874 which are not significant at alpha .05 level. This denotes that *bully and victim* do not significantly influence the self-efficacy of criminology students when left alone. However, the indicator *Pro-social* indicating positive social relationship with peers obtained the p-value less than 0.05. This means that with every point increase in the *self-efficacy*, there is also an increase of .500 in the *pro-social* aspect of bullying. It came out that pro-social is the domain that best influences bullying prevalence.

4. DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the discussion of the findings and its enumerated implications on bullying prevalence and self-efficacy among criminology students in General Santos City. Discussion on the topics is arranged according to the following: level of self-efficacy and bullying prevalence; correlation between self-efficacy and bullying prevalence; and multiple regression analysis on the influence between variables.

Self-Efficacy among Criminology Students

The variable self-efficacy is highly considered among the respondents from the three indicators: *Enlisting Social Resources*, *Academic Achievement*, and *Self-Regulated Learning*. The overall level of self-efficacy is high which means that self-efficacy oftentimes feel towards bullying prevalence. This further implies that criminology students have a high self-efficacy.

The indicator *Enlisting Social Resources* includes statement such as *Asking teacher for help when stuck on schoolwork*, *Asking another student for help when stuck on school work*, *Asking adults for help when having social problems*, *Asking a friend for help when having special problems*, *Asking a mentor for help when having social problems*. All of the statements were rated moderately by the respondents. Those groups of people who did not offer help had schools that were less compelling than they could be. Viability to make a positive school atmosphere is likewise an area in self-efficacy.

The second indicator of self-efficacy is *Academic achievement* includes statement such as *Learning criminalistics*, *Learning Criminal Law and Jurisprudence (CLJ)*, *Learning Crime Detection & Investigation (CDI)*, *Learning Law Enforcement Administration (LEA)*, *Learning Correctional Administration (CA)*, *Learning Sociology of Crimes Ethics and Human Relations*. All of the statements were rated high by the respondents. This signifies that criminology students learned a lot from their academics. This outcome is congruent with the views of Jahanian and Mahjoubi (2013) that there is a solid and considerable connection between self-viability and scholastic achievements with 99% certainty at high, center, low and low levels.

Another comparative examination led by Yazici, Seyisa and Altuna (2011) showed the impacts of enthusiastic knowledge and self-adequacy as influencers of scholarly accomplishment. They picked an example which included 407 understudies from secondary school level. Furthermore, scientists utilized The Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire, Self-Efficacy Beliefs Scale and a statistic data shape also. They found that distinctive factors like sex, age, familiarity with the feeling and continuing on to act elucidated scholastic achievement. They found that the most grounded indicator was the variable of continuing on to the carry on while the self-adequacy was considered as minor component. In view of that, specialists showed that there had been solid connections among the scholastic accomplishment and self-adequacy decidedly among understudies.

The finding is in consonance with the examination done by Loo and Choy (2013) about wellsprings of self-adequacy affecting scholastic accomplishment. They picked their example haphazardly, through which they picked diverse gadgets related confirmations in Republic Polytechnic. They found that each of the four self-adequacy sources was extensively identified with accomplishments in both of mathematic scores and total GPA of hardware related designing certificates. All the more essentially, they found that the factor of dominance encounter was the prime influencer of scholarly achievements of science and related building modules.

The third indicator of self-efficacy is *self-regulated learning*. This includes *finishing homework assignment by deadlines, always concentrating on school subjects during class, planning schoolwork for the day, taking good notes during class instruction, getting oneself to do schoolwork*. This shows that criminology students are very much focused on their academics. In a study of high school students, Labuhnet al.,(2010) found that students who were shown SRL abilities through checking and impersonation will probably inspire more elevated amounts of scholarly self-adequacy (i.e., certainty) and perform higher on proportions of scholastic accomplishment contrasted with understudies who did not get SRL guideline.

Bullying Prevalence among Criminology Students

The level of bullying prevalence among criminology students is moderate across three indicators where items per indicators show low and high descriptive level. This means that the bullying prevalence among criminology students is moderately considered by the respondents.

The indicator bully includes, *Students in the school; giving soft school/ classmates a hard time, going around teasing others, liking to make others scared, enjoying upsetting wimps, and liking to get in fights with someone they can easily beat*. All of these statements were rated by the respondents a low level. The implication of low level under the indicator bully shows that criminology students in General Santos City are experiencing low level of bullying. It indicates also, that criminology students are *pro-social*. This outcome is congruent with the view of Canty et al. (2014) who called the attention to that such 'preparing' may darken youngsters' genuine experience. It likewise ignores the way that every youngster is in a functioning procedure of 'understanding and generation of the way of life around them'. It is conceivable that youngsters may react to 'tormenting' as a stacked term related with grown-up produced ideas.

The second indicator of bullying is *victim* which includes statement such as *getting called names by others, getting picked on by others, making fun by others, getting hit and punished around others, leaving out things on purpose*. The aforementioned statements were regarded as moderate and low by the respondents with the overall descriptive level of low. This signifies that criminology students in General Santos City are sometimes victims in bullying situations. This outcome is congruent with the view of Tsunget. al, (2011) that victims of bullying are at an expanded danger of dropping out of school and failing scholastically which can prompt them getting to be engaged with groups and taking an interest in reprobate and hostile social conduct. In later life they may become troublesome maintaining unsound relationship and can wind up damaging companions and guardians. This can prompt them being at a higher danger of melancholy and suicide.

The third indicator of bullying which is *pro-social* was found to be highly rated among the respondents. This includes *liking to make friends, liking to help students being harassed, liking to share things with others, liking to help friends being harassed, and enjoying helping others*. This outcome is congruent with the views of Flooket al, (2015) that youngsters with prosocial propensities have a tendency to have sufficiently created dialect and social abilities. Youngsters who have created social abilities will probably have the capacity to control themselves. Self-regulation could help lighten issue conducts that happen after some time, for example, animosity. Kids with great self-control can pick up companionships and furthermore

diminish the probability of being bullied. Individuals with these specific arrangements of abilities are additionally ready to make fellowships all the more effortlessly.

Significance on the Relationship between Self-efficacy and Bullying Prevalence

Correlation between the two variables reveals a significant relationship between self-efficacy and bullying prevalence among criminology students. This implies that the bullying prevalence of criminology students is influenced by their self-efficacy. Significant positive relationship between bullying prevalence and self-efficacy was revealed in the test of relationship. The self-efficacy has a direct relationship with bullying as being shown likewise among the indicators of each of the variables. The bullying prevalence indicators, which are *bully, victim and pro-social* provided the positive significant relationship in the over-all association towards self-efficacy with indicators *enlisting social resources, academic achievement and self-regulated learning*.

From the results gathered, the point of the study is to test the relationship between variables and among indicators. Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between bullying prevalence and self-efficacy was therefore rejected. The findings of the study is anchored in theory presented in theoretical framework which is congruent with the views of Kokkinos and Kipritsi (2012) who stated that a man's self-adequacy in specific areas throughout their life can influence how they carry on in bullying circumstances. Individuals with high self-viability in scholarly exhibitions and social connection will probably manage issues in a safeguarding and nervousness free estate. It may be proposed that these individuals would acquire the part of the safeguard in bullying circumstances. Individuals with low self-adequacy in these areas will probably create maladaptive conduct and may probably take up the part of the domineering bully, partner to the bully or the victim. The findings is similar to the study of Thornberg and Jungert (2013) expressed that in their investigation large amounts of self-efficacy propelled and drew in teenagers to encourage the victim, while low levels of self-efficacy repressed them from mediating.

Significance on the Influence of Self-Efficacy on Bullying Prevalence among Criminology Students

A regression analysis was employed to determine the influence of self-efficacy towards bullying prevalence among criminology students. The data revealed that the overall self-efficacy significantly influence bullying prevalence among criminology students. The significant influences of self-efficacy are *Enlisting Social Resources, Academic Achievement and Self-Regulated Learning*. Asking a teacher for help when stuck on schoolwork, asking another student for help when stuck on school work, asking adults for help when having social problems, asking a friend for help when having special problems, asking a mentor for help when having social problems, learning criminalistics, learning Criminal Law and Jurisprudence (CLJ), learning Crime Detection & Investigation (CDI), learning Law Enforcement Administration (LEA), learning Correctional Administration (CA), learning Sociology of Crimes Ethics and Human Relations, finishing homework assignment by deadlines, always concentrating on school subjects during class, planning schoolwork for the day, taking good notes during class instruction, getting oneself to do schoolwork significantly influence the bullying prevalence of criminology students. This means that criminology students should focus more in enhancing their self-efficacy in order to lessen their bullying prevalence.

The result is congruent with the study conducted by Kassem (2015) on bullying behaviour and general self-efficacy among the studied nursing students, the result revealed that there was a significant relationship between bullying behaviour and general self-efficacy among the studied nursing students.

Self-efficacy of criminology students significantly influences the *pro-social* aspect of bullying. The result is congruent to the study of Tsung et al (2011). Research on self-efficacy and bullying recommends that self-efficacy decidedly influences star social conduct with understudies high in self-productivity convictions more inclined to help out the victim though those with low levels of self-efficacy convictions which are unquestionably liable to not intercede by any means.

5. CONCLUSION

This is the result of the conducted study on bullying prevalence and self-efficacy among criminology students in General Santos City as follows: the Level of self-efficacy among Criminology Students is high; the level of bullying prevalence among criminology students is moderate; there is a significant relationship between bullying prevalence and self-efficacy was revealed in the test of relationship and there is a significant influence between self-efficacy and bullying prevalence among criminology students.

The present finding revealed that there was a significance relationship between bullying prevalence and self-efficacy among the criminology students. This finding confirms the anchor theory of Kokkinos and Kipritsi, (2012) that individuals with large amounts of self-efficacy are more ready to manage issues in a safeguarding and uneasiness free estate. While individuals with low self-efficacy will probably create maladaptive practices which drive them to take up the part of the bully or the victim.

The result of the study also supports the study of Tsungetal. (2011) who proposed that elevated amounts of self-efficacy are related with the safeguard part and low levels of self-efficacy are related with the part of the domineering bully and the victim. The suggestion demonstrates the imperative part of self-efficacy in bullying commonness.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

The level of self-efficacy among criminology students is high; the researcher recommends that criminology schools design a program that can increase to a very high level of the self-efficacy of criminology students.

The level of bullying prevalence among criminology students is moderate; the researcher recommends that criminology schools design a program that can eradicate or lower the level of bullying prevalence and encourage the criminology students to be friendly.

There is a significant relationship between self-efficacy and bullying prevalence and there is a significant influence between self-efficacy and bullying prevalence among criminology students. The researcher, therefore recommend, that the Commission on Higher Education may formulate programs that will further increase the level of self-efficacy among criminology students towards the bullying prevalence. This implies that the CHED officials may orient Criminology schools/teachers about the purpose and value of self-efficacy. The researcher also recommends that criminology students increase their high level of self-efficacy because it would safeguard them from bullying situations and a further research regarding the other factors of self-efficacy and bullying prevalence may be conducted to validate the results of the present study.

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